

Gelation of polyacrylamide by Cr^{3+} : analysis of mechanism and thermal stability of the gel

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The crosslinking reaction between partially hydrolyzed polyacrylamide (HPAM) and Cr^{3+} was investigated. The reactive groups of HPAM were determined by FT-IR spectra. The viscosity and the transmittance of the gelling fluids were also measured through crosslinking process. The chromium ions reacted mainly with the carboxylic groups of HPAM and the hydrolysis degree (HD) of HPAM samples had a pronounced influence on the reaction rates. Differential scanning calorimetry and thermogravimetry were used to study the thermal stability of the resulting gels which exhibited much higher thermal stability than HPAM samples.

Aqueous gels formed by the Cr^{3+} crosslinking of partially hydrolyzed polyacrylamide (HPAM) have been commonly applied in petroleum industry. The low and predictable gelation rate of Cr^{3+} /HPAM solutions under most conditions renders them suitable for profile modification applications. The purpose is to block high permeable zones in the oil reservoir and divert flow into the regions of low permeability¹. TIORCO Inc. has applied this crosslinking system to 29 field projects, and 22 of the projects were considered successful, resulting in improved oil recovery and reduced water production². Although knowledge and control of the gelation time is extremely important in most of the intended application, only an incomplete understanding of the gelation kinetics and mechanism has been achieved to date.

Some authors³ reported that the crosslinking reaction occurs through ionic bonding between positive multivalent metal ions such as Al^{3+} or Cr^{3+} and the negative sites of a polymer such as carboxylic groups of HPAM or biopolymer. The carboxylic groups originate from hydrolyzed amide functions of the polyacrylamide. Cr^{3+} is used as organically chelated Cr^{3+} compounds. Organic chelating ions, such as acetate, malonate and propionate, protect highly active Cr^{3+} species by forming a coordinate-covalent bonded Cr^{3+} -carboxylate complex and, thus, provide delay to a gel system. The gelation is believed to occur via a ligand-exchange process⁴. The rate of the polymer crosslinking reaction/ligand exchange is determined by the rate of dissociation of the ligand from Cr^{3+} complex⁴⁻⁶. Other authors

reported that non-hydrolyzed polyacrylamide/ Cr^{3+} acetate aqueous gelling system acts as water shutoff and injectivity profile modification. The thermal stability of the resulting gels is a most important factor influencing the gel application properties. If the gel is more stable at high temperature under oil reservoir conditions, it may improve the oil production and reduce the usage of the polymer.

In order to identify the reacting groups of HPAM and to study the thermal stability of the resulting gel system, inorganic Cr^{3+} was used as the crosslinking agent in the present study. We used IR spectroscopic methods and viscosity measurement to investigate the process of Cr^{3+} /HPAM crosslinking system. To our knowledge, the thermal stability of the resulting gels has been firstly measured by DSC and TG.

Results and Discussion

Evidence of crosslinking by FT-IR spectra : Fig. 1 shows the IR-spectra of the polyacrylamide samples and the resulting gels. The spectra revealed bonds at 1677 (amide), 1610 (OH of COOH), 1571, 1411 cm^{-1} (C=O of polyacrylic unit)⁵. For the sample with hydrolysis degree (HD) = 26.0%, when it was mixed with Cr^{3+} , the 1571 cm^{-1} band disappeared and the intensity of the band at 1411 cm^{-1} was reduced. In the case of the sample with HD = 2.4%, when it was mixed with Cr^{3+} solution, there was no significant change at the 1571 and 1411 cm^{-1} bands compared with HPAM sample. So Cr^{3+} reacts mainly with carboxylic groups of the HPAM rather than amide groups.

Fig. 1. IR spectra of HPAM samples and the resulting gels : (1) TONGDE sample (HD = 2.4%), (2) TONGDE sample (HD = 2.4%) resulting gel, (3) TONGDE sample (HD = 26.0%), (4) TONGDE sample (HD = 26.0%) resulting gel.

Viscosity studies : Wang *et al.*⁸ measured some kinetic parameter of gelation for the HPAM sol in the presence of a comparatively high dose of Cr^{3+} and found that the gelation process could be divided into three stages : acceleration, steady-state and final. We investigated the effect of hydrolysis degree (HD) of HPAM on the viscosity of the gelation process (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Variation of viscosity with time for HPAM/ Cr^{3+} , conc. in polymer = 5 g/L; conc. in Cr^{3+} = 0.1 g/L.

When HD of HPAM is 2.4%, there is actually no change in viscosity for the gelation process. In the case of 18.0%, there exists an induction period before gelation starts. For the crosslinking system of HD 26.1%, one observes rising of viscosity at the beginning. As a general rule of thumb, the change of viscosity indicates the gelation process of the crosslinking system. Wang *et al.*⁸ used the time-dependence of the apparent viscosity to analyze the kinetics of polyacrylamide sol with chromium ions.

It is well known that the hydrolysis degree indicates the weight content of polyacrylic units in all the molecules. If HD is very low, it means that there is very low content of $\text{COO}^- \text{Na}^+$ in the polymer molecules. From the results described above, at the same concentration HPAM and Cr^{3+} , the sample of high HD reacts relatively much faster with Cr^{3+} than the sample of low HD. So we think that Cr^{3+} can react with COO^- at ambient temperature. On the other hand, due to the rapid reaction between inorganic Cr^{3+} and HPAM, for which hydrolysis degree is usually in the range 5–30%, it is necessary to develop the slow-gelling HPAM/ Cr^{3+} systems for in-depth treatment^{4,5}.

Transmittance studies : It has been suggested that a shoulder in the UV-region at 264 nm can be used in the monitoring of the Cr^{3+} /HPAM reaction⁹. The wavelength to study the reaction between Cr^{3+} and HPAM was chosen as 570 nm⁷. For convenience, we choose the transmittance rather than absorbance to study the reaction between Cr^{3+} and HPAM.

Fig. 3 shows that there is only small change in transmittance of the reaction system of the sample (HD = 2.4%). There is a sharp decrease in transmittance at the beginning for the reaction system of the sample (HD = 26.1%). In the case of HD = 18%, the transmittance gradually decreases with the time, but the final transmittance is higher than that of the reaction system of the sample (HD = 26.1%). According to Allain and Salome⁹, the interaction between

Fig. 3. Transmittance curves of reaction systems.

HPAM and Cr^{3+} proceeds by substitution; one or more of the six initial ligands of the Cr^{3+} ions, which are OH_2 , OH^- , or Cl^- , can be substituted by the $^- \text{OOC}$ groups of the acrylic monomer residues. Such a substitution modifies the UV-visible spectrum of Cr^{3+} : a variation of the absorbance and a shift of the peaks in the visible range were observed. If the polymer contains more carboxylic groups, the substitution rates will be faster than that of polymer with lower hydrolysis degree.

TG analysis : We have investigated the reaction between Cr^{3+} and HPAM using thermal analysis (TG) for the first time. The thermograms of HPAM samples and the resulting gels are shown in Fig. 4. Table 1 shows the weight-loss and three transition points. It can be seen that the gels exhibit higher thermal stability than HPAM samples. This is attributed to the reaction between Cr^{3+} and HPAM and the formation of three-dimensional networks

Fig. 4. Schematic TG thermograms of HPAM samples and their corresponding reaction systems : (A) HPAM (HD = 2.4%), (B) HPAM (HD = 26.1%), (C) HPAM (HD = 2.4%) + Cr^{3+} , (D) HPAM (HD = 26.1%) + Cr^{3+} .

(because of the weight ratio being HPAM : Cr^{3+} = 50 : 1, the effect of Cr^{3+} considered as a substance on the thermal stability can be neglected). For example, the weight-loss of the HPAM sample with HD = 26.0% is 70.99%, whereas that of its gel is 27.05%.

At the first transition point ($\sim 50^\circ$), the sample lost the remained water. At the second transition point ($\sim 260^\circ$), the long-chain polymer molecules or the structure of the crosslinks fractured acutely. At first, for the HPAM, the side-groups of amide and/or carboxylic groups may be liberated from the main chain of the polymer. In the case of the gels, the three-dimensional polymer network may be decomposed. After the third transition point ($\sim 350^\circ$), the polymer or the structure of the crosslinks was destroyed.

Table 1. Weight-loss and three transition points in Fig. 4

Sample	A ^a	B	C	D
Weight-loss, %	73.51	70.99	20.64	27.05
First transition point, °C	45.06	50.54	52.19	50.3
Second transition point, °C	255.68	260.36	266.93	263.26
Third transition point, °C	350.95	324.00	379.74	371.38

^aA-HPAM (2.4%) ; B-HPAM (26.0%) ; C-HPAM (2.4%) + Cr^{3+} ; D-HPAM (26.0%) + Cr^{3+} .

Comparing the two gels, the result is not consistent with that we expected. The weight-loss of the gel of HPAM with higher HD is a little higher than that of the gel of HPAM with lower HD. Han *et al.*¹⁰ reported that at elevated temperature, the non-hydrolyzed polyacrylamide was hydrolyzed to convert some amide groups to carboxylic ones and so attained a certain hydrolyzed degree, then the gelation took place. However, Cr^{3+} also reacts with the carboxylic groups in HPAM. Maybe the higher contents of carboxylic groups result in the overcrosslinking of the reaction system and the non-uniformity of the three-dimensional networks, and the decomposition occurs at the weak points. Further experiments are needed to check this hypothesis. In the meantime, we consider that a suitable lower hydrolysis degree of HPAM helps to improve the thermal stability of the reaction systems.

DSC analysis : DSC has been very useful to explain the thermal stability of polymers. The results of HPAM samples and the resulting gels are presented in Fig. 5 and Table 2. It can be seen that for low hydrolysis HPAM sample, there is a little change in the heat absorption range and heat capacity compared with the gel. In the case of HPAM with high hydrolysis degree, the absorption range is

Fig. 5. DSC thermograms of HPAM samples and their corresponding reaction systems. Curve A, HPAM (HD = 26.1%); B, HPAM (HD = 26.1%) + Cr^{3+} ; C, HPAM (HD = 2.4%); D, HPAM (HD = 2.4%) + Cr^{3+} .

delayed to high temperature and the heat capacity is much lower than the HPAM sample due to the crosslinking network caused by the reaction between carboxylic groups and Cr^{3+} .

Table 2. Heat absorption range and heat capacity

Sample	Heat abs. range ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Heat capacity (J^{-1}g)
HPAM (2.4%)	201.23 ~ 347.56	811.0
HPAM (2.4%) + Cr^{3+}	193.29 ~ 396.78	878.99
HPAM (26.0%)	180.89 ~ 331.62	779.38
HPAM (26.0%) + Cr^{3+}	192.80 ~ 390.79	443.38

Conclusions : At ambient temperature, the crosslinking reaction between HPAM and Cr^{3+} occurred through the complexation of Cr^{3+} with carboxylic groups on the HPAM molecules. In the case of non-hydrolyzed polyacrylamide, the reaction between Cr^{3+} and polyacrylamide was not observed for a limited period of time. While at elevated temperature, the polyacrylamide was first hydrolyzed to a certain hydrolysis degree and then reacted with Cr^{3+} . The gels exhibited much higher thermal stability than HPAM samples. Further studies are required on the effect of hydrolysis degree on the thermal stability of the HPAM/ Cr^{3+} crosslinking systems.

Experimental

The commercial polyacrylamide sample TONGDE of MW 3.0×10^6 (Tongde Chemical Co., Dalian, China) was used. ^{13}C NMR study showed the polymer to be 2.4% hydrolyzed. A 1% polymer solution was added to acetone and the precipitated purified polymer was separated from the solution by means of centrifugation. The TONGDE samples were further hydrolyzed under alkaline conditions to 18.0 and 26.1%. Cr^{3+} solution was prepared from $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and placed for several days before use. The stock polymer solutions were prepared by gentle stirring with magnetic stirrer in distilled water containing 5g/L NaCl. The pH of the solution was adjusted by addition of aqueous HCl or NaOH.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were obtained from a Nicolet 20SX FTIR spectrophotometer.

Viscosity was measured with NDJ-1 viscometer (Balance Instrument Factory, Shanghai) at room temperature. The experiments were made under the lowest shear rate to avoid the destruction of the gelling network.

Thermogravimetry (TG) experiments were carried out using a Rheometric machine with a sample weight of around 10 mg. The sample was a powder made from a sol or gel, and the water was removed at 65° . The analysis was carried out in N_2 atmosphere from 10 to 500° at a heating rate of $10^{\circ}/\text{min}^{-1}$ with N_2 flow rate of 50 ml/min. Thermograms were obtained by plotting percent residual weight against temperature. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments were performed using a Perkin-Elmer DSC7 instrument with N_2 flow rate of 50 ml/min. The samples was scanned at a rate of 10° between 10 and 420° .

The transmittance of the sol-gel was recorded with a 7211 spectrophotometer (Second Analytical Instrument Factory, Shanghai, China) at the wavelength of 570 nm. Distilled water was used as reference.

References

1. M. K. Thore, R. Peter and K. Jostein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1995, **99**, 8255.
2. J. C. Mack and J. E. Smith, 1994, *SPE/DOE* 27780.
3. A. Moradi-Araghi, G. Bjornson and P. H. Doe, *SPE Adv. Tech. Ser.*, 1993, **1**, 140.
4. T. P. Lockhart and P. Albonicao, 1992, *SPE/DOE* 24194.
5. T. P. Lockhart, P. Albonicao and G. Burrofato, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1991, **43**, 1527.
6. P. Albonico, G. Burrofato, A. D. Lullo and T. P. Lockhart, 1993, *SPE* 25221.
7. T. M. Klaveness and P. Ruoff, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1994, **98**, 10119.
8. G. X. Wang, Z. H. Wang and Z. Q. Chen, *Chin. J. Chem.*, 1995, **13**, 97.
9. C. Allain and L. Salome, *Macromolecules*, 1990, **23**, 981.
10. M. Han, L. Shi, M. Ye and J. Ma, *Polym. Bull.*, 1995, **35**, 99.